

COST ESTIMATES OF COMPOSITE AEROSPACE STRUCTURES BASED ON COMPLEXITY

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SUMMARY : The focus of this paper is a computer based system for measuring the complexity of a composite part, based on information theory, according to a model from MIT. Metrics such as geometric complexities and laminate complexities are considered, and these will be read from files of the Patran™ Laminate Modeler. Other metrics known as extensible parameters will be read from the files generated by CAD (Computer Aided Design). All these metrics are calculated and stored in an OODBMS (Object Oriented Database). These complexity metrics will then be retrieved and incorporated into the MIT cost model to predict the cost to manufacture a particular composite component. With this system, cost predictions will be readily available during the preliminary design phase.

KEYWORDS: computer aided design and manufacture, cost estimation, design

INTRODUCTION

Advanced composites have had considerable impact on the aircraft industry due to their low weight and high strength, as well as the flexibility they offer in designing parts with specific structural properties. However, this has been hampered by their high material and fabrication costs. Studies indicate that a large percentage of the final cost is determined in the design phase, and a major cost driver in composite manufacturing is the complexity of the part.

The aim of this project is to develop a computer based system for measuring the complexity of a part, based on information theory, according to a model from MIT[1]. The MIT complexity model has been manually verified. (Further verification is still under investigation.) The computer based model will reproduce the manually generated results that have been obtained to date. The inputs to the system are CAD (Computer Aided Design) data of the component from Microstation™ [17] and from the Patran™ Laminate Modeler [18].

Extensible parameters such as volume, surface area, perimeter, and dimensions, etc. of the design will be obtained from the CAD system. These parameters are used in first order (zero complexity) cost calculations. Geometric complexities of composite parts, like stretch and shrink flange angles, and laminate complexities, such as ply counts, drop off plies, and ply orientations are being determined from the Patran Laminate Modeler.

This paper will describe how the extensible parameters are calculated and retrieved from the CAD System. It also explains how the curvature of the complex surface and the laminate complexities are determined from the Patran Laminate Modeler. The complexity of a part increases manufacturing time beyond the first order or zero complexity prediction. Ply drop-offs and multiple ply orientations require more cutting and more pieces per unit volume. Complex curvature parts are more difficult to manufacture as they imply a change in manufacturing procedures, especially more manual effort.

All these complexity metrics will be calculated and stored in an OODBMS(object oriented database). The complexity metrics are then retrieved and incorporated into the MIT cost model to predict, during preliminary design, the cost to manufacture a particular composite component. Details of the approach are provided in this paper.

BACKGROUND

M.I.T Model

It was shown that complex parts require more fabrication time than simpler parts[3]. The MIT Cost Model [2] incorporate complexity factors, and demonstrates that each complexity factor is unique and is either empirically or intuitively derived and is usually a process specific multivariable parameter. Muter[1] proposed an approach to define part complexity based on the idea that the information required to make a part is embodied in the detail part drawings, and, further, that complexity is completely determined by information content. An information theory approach is therefore taken to quantify the complexity associated with each nonredundant dimension on a part drawing. The information content of a part is then the sum of the individual dimension information terms, given by Eqn 1.

$$I = \sum_{i=1}^N \log_2 \left(\frac{\text{dimension}}{\text{tolerance}} \right) \quad (1)$$

Cost estimates produced using this equation were found to exhibit a similar degree of accuracy when compared to estimates performed by an experienced estimator [1].

It was shown[2] that measurements of complexity for composites were simplified by the fact that the constitution of the material, in terms of fiber volume fractions and fiber arrangements, was predetermined by the designer. Tse[2] developed a model for estimating manufacturing time which predicts recurring labor for a range of advanced composite material manufacturing processes for aircraft fuselage stiffeners. The model used an information metric for shape complexity. Tse chose the fibers to be the information carriers and identified three kinds of fiber information: bending, torsion and alignment or positioning.

Information Content of Composite Fibers

Fig. 1 shows the discrete model of an individual fiber. The model is based upon the use of a linear detector to measure discrete angle changes. The model assumes an equiprobable angular range of θ , and a minimum linear detection distance of δ . The minimum angular unit is denoted by ζ . The information content of one discrete fiber bend based on Eqn 1 is given by Eqn 2

$$I = \log_2 \left(\frac{\theta_{\max}}{\zeta} \right) \quad (2)$$

The total information content for a single curve of a fiber of radius ρ , of length S , which consists of N independent bends is given by Eqn 3

$$I = N \log_2 \left(\frac{\theta_{\max}}{\sqrt{\frac{\delta}{2\rho}}} \right) = \theta \sqrt{\frac{2\rho}{\delta}} \log_2 \left(\frac{\theta_{\max}}{\sqrt{\frac{\delta}{2\rho}}} \right) \quad (3)$$

Fig. 1: Discretization of a single curve in a fiber [2].

Fig. 2: Torsion in a single fiber [2]

Hence the information stored in curved fiber is linearly proportional to the enclosed angle θ . Further, the information, I , of the part is simply the sum of the information for all the fibers in the part.

Torsion Information

Torsion information is a measure of the amount of twist introduced in a fiber during forming.

Torsion information of Fig. 2 is given in Eqn 4.

$$\tau(s) = k(s) \tan(\alpha)$$

$$\phi = \tau L$$

$$I_{\text{torsion}} = \frac{\phi}{\zeta} \log_2 \left(\frac{\zeta}{\phi_{\max}} \right) \quad (4)$$

The angle of attack α relates the radius of torsional curvature to the bending curvature of the line, $k(s)$. ϕ is the angle of twist and L is the length. Though torsional information was found to be quantifiable, its effect on labor time appeared to be small. That is, parts with different amounts of calculated torsional information did not display an appreciable difference in labor forming time.

Positioning Information

Positioning information represents the probability of placing adjoining fibers in certain positions relative to each other. Positioning information is at a minimum when identical elements are butted against each other. Positioning information identifies the complexity in aligned fiber parts with no fiber bending. The part shown in Fig. 3 (a) has been defined to have no positioning information. The part in Fig. 3 (b) will have information based on the relative rotation of the fibers at the corner.

It has been shown[4] the complexity that arises in the lay-up of composite laminates is associated with the location and placement of successive plies on top of one another. In the ply configuration of a particular part, the lay-up of plies can be considered as a stack on N

Fig. 3: (a) Ply arrangement without measurable information content. (b) Ply arrangement having positioning information but no bending information [2]

Fig. 4: Various ply stack-ups [4]

elements, where each element is a ply. As shown in Fig. 4(a), if all N elements are identical, only one configuration is possible. In order to quantify this type of complexity, from an information theory approach, the probability of this configuration is 1. If there are m different ply sizes or shapes the number of possible configuration also changes. Fig. 4(b) shows two different configurations for the same N and m. The information content of a ply stack-up is given in Eqn 5 as

$$p = \frac{1}{m^N}$$

$$I = \log_2 \left(\frac{1}{p} \right) = \log_2 (m^N) = N \log_2 m \quad (5)$$

m types of plies are abstracted as ply drop-offs plus one from a design. Eqn 5 can be rewritten as:

$$I = (\# \text{ of plies}) \times \log(\# \text{ of ply dropoffs} + 1) \quad (6)$$

Summary of Labor Time

The first order model or zero complexity model for labor time is characterised by a time constant, τ and a final velocity, v_o [2]. The first order model is based on the idea that labourers can attain a final velocity for any task, and that their time to complete is a function of this velocity and an extensible parameter of the component to be built. The process task time for a large distance x , is given by the simple Eqn 7 [2]. The time constant, τ , is given by Eqn 8 [2].

$$T = \tau + \frac{X}{v_o} \quad (7)$$

$$\tau = \tau_o (1 + bI) \quad (8)$$

The constants τ_o and b are determined by the process. I is the scaling parameter that represents the complexity of the part. Tse[2] reported that for the manual hand lay-up process the time constant equation is given by Eqn 9

$$\tau = \tau_o (1 + b_m I_m + b_f I_f) \quad (9)$$

Where the subscript m refers to male type bends and the subscript f refers to female type bends. For additive processes such as tape lay-up, the time taken for n strips of width w and length x_i , for a ply, is given in terms of area A ,

$$T = \sum t = \sum_1^n \left(\tau + \frac{x_i}{v_o} \right) = n\tau + \frac{1}{v_o} \sum_1^n (x_i) = n\tau + \frac{A}{v_o w} \quad (10)$$

For N plies of thickness h , the time to make a part is given in terms of part volume V ,

$$T = \sum_1^N \sum_1^n t = nN\tau + \frac{V}{v_o wh} \quad (11)$$

The Eqn 11 is further reduced to a time-weight relation by introducing material density, as shown in Eqn 12,

$$T = nN\tau + \frac{W}{v_o wh\rho} \quad (12)$$

The Eqns 10, 11 and 12 form the basis of the MIT cost estimation model, first presented by Tse[2]. Depending on the nature of a particular part or process, any of these equations can be applied.

METHODOLOGY COMPUTER MODEL

A cost model for composite manufacture should incorporate measures of complexity that a designer can easily abstract from a design with readily available design tools. The computer system under development for the CRC -AS in Australia aims to accomplish this. The computer model is based on object oriented techniques. Each component and its

measurements (extensible parameters and complexities) are considered as objects. The advantages of this concept is that it provides extensibility in terms of components, measurements and processes in the model [12][15].

CAD SYSTEM

The CAD system used for the analysis is Microstation™ 95, which was chosen for its ease of use. The design models can easily be exported and imported to or from any other CAD system by the standard Initial Graphics Exchange Specification(IGES) format. Microstation features extensive measuring capabilities for extensible parameters through a macro library called Microstation Basic. This provides access to the memory block of Microstation, where the measurements such as dimensions, surface area, volume, etc are stored. These parameters are then written into a database. Microstation also provides the designer with an easy to use graphical user interface to facilitate user inputs for a component's name or measurements.

The designer has to select the appropriate component from the CAD design model and this in turn invokes Microstation to take measurements. These measurements are then written into a text file for export to the database by invoking a macro written in Microstation Basic.

Patran™ Laminate Modeler

Patran is an open, integrated CAE (Computer Aided Engineering) software system which enable a common model for analysis. It shortens the design process by eliminating the need for engineers to recreate design geometry for analysis. The Patran Laminate Modeler is a Patran module for aiding the design, analysis, and manufacture of laminated composite structures. The user can simulate the application of layers of reinforcing materials to selected areas of a surface to ensure that a design is realisable. Layers are then used to build up the composite construction in a manner that reflects the manufacture of the structure. Finite element properties and laminate materials are automatically generated so that accurate models of the structure can be evaluated rapidly. By enabling the concept of concurrent engineering, the Laminate Modeler facilitates the design of structures which take full advantage of these materials in the aerospace, automotive, marine, and other markets. It also defines fiber orientations.

Theory

The curvature of the fiber on the part surface is represented by in plane and out of plane curvature [3]. Normal or out of plane curvature is the type of curvature required to make singly curved parts (simple bends). Inplane curvature, or geodesic curvature, represents double or compound curvature parts. Hence over a section of constant curvature, the enclosed angle θ is

$$\theta^2 = \theta_n^2 + \theta_g^2 \quad (13)$$

where θ_n is the enclosed angle, for the out-of -plane bending of a fiber, and θ_g is the in-plane enclosed angle. For parts with different degrees of curvature, the in-plane enclosed angle is given by[3]

$$\bar{\theta}_g = \frac{1}{A} \sum \theta_{gi} \Delta A_i \quad (14)$$

A is the total area of the part, θ_{gi} is the enclosed angle for a given fiber or a region, and ΔA_i is the corresponding area for that fiber or that region. On a fiber by fiber basis, the equation is given as

$$\bar{\theta}_g = \frac{1}{A} \sum_{i=1}^{N_f} \theta_{gi} s_i \Delta s_n \quad (15)$$

s_i is the length of the fiber and Δs_n is the width of the fiber unit. N_f is the number of fibers. The enclosed angle θ_n (out-of-plane bend angle) for any arbitrary fiber orientation is given [2] in Eqn 16. Ψ is the fiber orientation angle, α is the angle between the two planes or surfaces.

$$\theta_n = \pi - 2 \cos^{-1} \left[\sin \psi \cos \left(\frac{\alpha}{2} \right) \right] \quad (16)$$

Out-of-plane and in-plane shear slip required to deform an initially flat laminate into their respective enclosed angles is illustrated in Fig. 5. It was shown by Tam and Gutowski in [11], the shear slip for the appropriate plane is defined as

$$\Gamma = \frac{\delta}{H} \quad (17)$$

Hence from [11]

$$\theta = \Gamma \quad (18)$$

Incremental shear from a fiber mapping is defined as

$$d\Gamma_{12} = \frac{ds_1 - ds_0}{du} \quad (19)$$

ds_0 and ds_1 are incremental lengths along two adjacent fibers, and du is the inter-fiber spacing as shown in Fig. 6. It was shown that the in-plane shear deformation is related to the geodesic curvature of a fiber as

$$\Gamma_{12} = \int_0^L k_s(s) ds \quad (20)$$

Fig. 5: Shear slip required to deform a flat laminate in the appropriate plane [11].

Fig. 6: In-plane local incremental shear [11].

By using Eqns 13, 16, 19 and 20, the enclosed angle is calculated numerically.

Ply drop-offs for different ply orientations are calculated using the equations derived by Neoh E.T [3]. These use the extensible parameters that are being calculated and stored in a text file by Microstation. The fiber orientation and ply count are read from the files that are generated in the Patran Laminate Modeler.

Summary of the Method

The CAD data of the component in standard IGES file format will be input into Patran™. The advantages of using the Patran Laminate Modeler is that it generates files that have information about the lay-up details such as fiber orientation, warp and weft fibers, ply count and the fiber thickness. Though the file in the Laminate Modeler does not give the fiber enclosed angle (as shown in Fig. 1) directly, it can be numerically calculated with the knowledge of the warp and weft fiber co-ordinates.

The surface to be laid with composite material is first meshed using finite elements. Using the laminate modeler tool, lay-up is carried out. The designer needs to input the composite material, the warp and weft angle if scissor draping is selected and also the thickness of a single ply. The laminate material and its properties are defined using the standard Patran methods of material definition. Once the reference direction is specified for the fiber placement, the ply lay-up will be done and the files containing information about the fibers will be exported. During the analysis, it is possible to visually observe the amount of strain on the surface of the part. This is indicated by different colours, with each specific colour representing the percentage of the maximum strain. This indicates the difficulty of lay-up and also it gives the pattern of the lay-up fabric.

DATABASE

After evaluation, ply drop off and fiber angle is written into a text file. This text file is then used to export this data to an ObjectStore [16] database that has the cost calculating equations [12].

ObjectStore is a comprehensive object oriented database management system (OODBMS). It is based on the storage of entities as objects. The advantages of using this kind of database are the following [12][15]: a) Since the entities are stored as objects, different kind of entities can be stored in the database, and the objects can be interrelated in ways that go beyond the relational model. b) It provides extensibility in terms of the number and kind of objects. This means that any number of measurements and components can be stored in the database. c) This system uses the powerful features of object oriented analysis, design and implementation such as polymorphism, delegation, containment, inheritance, etc. With an object oriented approach, the data and behavior are fully integrated. This results in a superior representation than one that could be done with a relational approach, especially for manufacturing applications.

The problem has been analysed using object oriented methodology[13][14]. OMT(Object Modeling Technique, developed by Raumbaugh[13]) notations shown in Fig. 7 is used in building the object model shown in Fig. 8.

Fig. 7: Basic notation used in Object Model.

Fig. 8: The Object Oriented Model of the Complexity Metrics

The Object model shown in Fig. 8 describes an Object Oriented Interface between a CAD system and an OODBMS. There are eight classes in this model. The class Measurements is a superclass for Extensible_Parameters and Complexity_Metrics. It has commonality in terms of attributes and behaviour for the two sub-classes. The class Extensible_Parameter (inherited from Measurements) specialises its behaviour to take the Extensible Parameters from the CAD system (like length, area, volume, etc).

The class Complexity_Metrics (inherited from Measurements) specialises its behaviour to take Complexity Metrics from the Laminate Modeler. It has two subclasses Geometric_Complexity and Laminated_Complexity. Each of them specialises in the type of complexities (geometric or laminate). However each of these classes use the extensible parameters stored in the database to calculate complexities (uses Database).

The class Database is a superclass for Database_Query describing the interface for the database operations (like opening a database, writing data to a database and closing the database). The subclass Database_Query (inherits from Database) describes the interface for the querying operations to be performed by the user in the event of changing of any data in the database. The class Interface describes the interface for transferring the data from the CAD system and Laminate Modeler. It essentially describes a link list that is later stored in the database (uses Database).

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The system developed will automatically generate complexity metrics like extensible parameters, curvature angle, and laminate complexities. These complexity metrics are stored in an OODBMS and then will be retrieved and input into the cost equations[12]. These equations give fabrication time, which takes care of geometric complexities and laminate complexities of the part. Knowing the fabrication time, actual cost of the component can be determined at the design stage.

Most of the computer based system has been designed and implemented, although full integration to the Patran Laminate Modeler has not yet been completed. The cost predictions have been verified in the USA, and some verification has been carried out in Australia. However, additional work with CRC industrial partners is being done currently. Case studies, including an aircraft carriage door, are under investigation.

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